

What is the Point? Assessing Emotional Engagement with Interactive Jewellery Using the POINT Framework.

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Full Paper

Abstract

The use of a familiar object (jewellery) to access creative onscreen content has the potential to engage new audiences and create new insights and experiences at the interface between artefacts and multimedia applications. This paper discusses a research project which uses a hybrid of craft, visual art and human factors methods to investigate emotional responses to interaction with screen-based content using jewellery as a tangible interface.

Jewellery has been the focus of technological research as a carrier of ubiquitous computing by non-jewellery specialists, but the use and adaptation of existing forms of jewellery tends to ignore the rich potential within the jewellery object as a carrier of multilayered meaning: the aesthetics of the artefact and the emotional quality of the interaction are often secondary considerations to the efficacy of technology. On the other hand, within Contemporary Jewellery, evaluation frameworks as understood within other disciplines, simply do not exist: analysis of objects and their reception by wearers is based on implicit knowledge, and subjective assumptions. This research utilises the Point Framework, developed for human factors research in a business environment to investigate users' emotional responses to interactive jewellery.

The researchers, a multimedia artist and a jewellery designer have produced prototypes of both jewellery and onscreen applications to facilitate dialogue between themselves and users/wearers to explore the relationship between engagement and interactivity, between screen and artefact. The resultant multimedia and artefact simulation allow the user to experience surprising and engaging interactions between tangible input and screen output.

Findings suggest that using jewellery to initiate and control interaction with multimedia applications can create emotional experiences and new relationships between tangible objects and virtual interactions. The research demonstrates that the distinctive methods inherent in visual art and craft practice can be synthesised with user-centred methodologies to have relevance to contemporary issues outside the traditional concerns and domain of craft and visual art.

Keywords: Interaction, jewellery, multimedia, wearables, user centred design, POINT Framework

Introduction

The use of a familiar object (jewellery) to access creative onscreen content has the potential to engage new audiences and create new insights and experiences at the interface between artefacts and multimedia applications. This paper discusses a research project which uses a hybrid of craft, visual art and human factors methods to investigate emotional responses to interaction with screen-based content using jewellery as a tangible interface.

Jewellery is a relevant vehicle for exploring issues of interactivity, as Kettley (2004) suggests, the 'craft object' lends itself to being placed within an interactive context, because it can combine familiarity (of form) with newness (of function). Interactive multimedia content, in this context, must reflect and extend the wearers experience of the worn object and in doing so both physical object and digital content are redefined.

Context

The jewellery object has been the focus of technological research by Philips, Nike and IBM as a carrier of ubiquitous computing. However, the use and adaptation of existing forms of jewellery by non-jewellery specialists, tends to ignore the rich potential within the jewellery object as a carrier of multilayered meaning: an earring simply becomes an earpiece. The aesthetics of the artefact and the emotional quality of the interaction are often secondary considerations to the efficacy of technology. Practice – in this context the production of jewellery artefacts and multimedia content becomes a vehicle for exploring user needs. User input can be quickly assimilated into each stage of the investigation. The value of the jeweller as investigator is in the understanding of wearability, in the context of adornment, as opposed to simple functionality. This encompasses an understanding of material properties, manufacturing techniques, cultural associations and issues of attachment. Jewellery objects create a sense of attachment, beyond the surface functionality of the object (adornment) through the meaning signified by the jewellery as love token, a memento or an indicator of social status or wealth. The research demonstrates that jewellery is a relevant vehicle for exploring issues of multimedia interactivity and physical computing.

Engagement with interactive multimedia, in its many forms, has become a significant human activity. Mainstream digital design uses multimedia experience to engage users with digital content that is, for the most part, referencing mainstream contemporary culture and is

symbolic of global experience; emotional engagement takes place within collective experience. Individual multimedia practitioners, like their jeweller counterparts, can explore subject areas and employ technical/craft approaches that engage with individual and select groups of users; the experienced multimedia artist/designer who is able to make unique creative connections between different elements of digital process - in this case algorithmic animation/sound and sensor data - can create virtual objects in a manner consistent with craft traditions, where individual knowledge of material properties is intimately connected to the development of object form and meaning Steel (2004). Traditional craft is concerned with the physicality of objects in the world. Digital design is concerned with the manipulation and experience of virtual data. This research seeks to develop a new hybrid practice that is a synthesis of both the jeweller's craft and individual approaches to multimedia design. This new synthesis redefines subsequent object and digital content in terms of user/wearer experience.

The Jewellery Object

The mode and purpose of wearing jewellery makes it an appropriate choice as a controlling device in physical computing. Jewellery is worn close to, or directly on the body, within the wearer's personal space, giving it an intimacy that is absent from other wearable devices (Wallace and Dearden 2005).

Watkins (1999) states that in wearing a piece of jewellery:

"The sensation of touch on the body is pre-eminent, but movement and gesture, signal and message also become active participants in a web of visual, physical and psychological elements".

One of the key roles of jewellery is as a carrier of narrative. Game (2004) suggests that for jewellery to tell its story, it needs a wearer who is an active participant in the narrative. Moignard (2004) suggests that even within an abstract piece of jewellery, the viewer will try to find links and patterns within a piece and attempt to see it as a signifier of something beyond the object itself. This analysis extends beyond the materiality of the object and the intention of the maker and wearer to the circumstances in which the jewellery was obtained: whether as a family heirloom, a personal purchase or a treasured gift. The circumstances of acquisition allow the viewer to create an emotional narrative giving indications of the wearer's taste, emotional attachments and sense of status and insight into personal relationships with the gift giver.

The Digital Object

Berghaus (2002) states: “whenever new technology serves the archaic nature of mankind it succeeds.” In all periods of art and across cultures the patterns observed in natural and man-made structures have been central to the development of culturally significant visual schemata. A significant strand in digital creativity makes a direct connection between visual imagery and software structure: generative art and algorithmic animation are expressions of an aesthetic response to software structures that simultaneously reflect machine and organic process. Steel’s approach to the design of multimedia embraces this aesthetic while recognising that a more traditional narrative, building on historical context and physical sensation, can stimulate a deeper emotional connection in a potential user/wearer. The visual expression of body movement and recognition of viewer position relative to art object has been a major theme and concern in western art. Computer based motion detection scenarios enable the development of digital content that echo or reinforce physical presence and can be seen as a continuation of the intimate relationship between the body and art object. Willats (1997) has noted that, throughout art history, anomaly in picture representation has always been used as an expressive tool by artists and designers and its use stimulates an emotional response in the observer. When we make new connections between physical and virtual objects we create anomaly. Altering pre-conceived notions and expectations of what a digital object should be, what it should represent and relate to, and how it should behave in certain contexts is a significant part of this and future research.

Narratives and Audience

One of the major limitations to user experience of screen interactivity is the lack of complimentary and enriching physical interactions to digital content. New digital innovations that employ motion detection and tangible interfaces (Sony's EyeToy, smart whiteboards, the tablet-pc etc.) are tackling this problem within the boundaries of contemporary digital culture and business practice. This project is a means by which computer interactivity can find a new physical manifestation and a fresh cultural reference point.

Peacock (2004) suggests that interactivity is inherently narrative. Cause and effect created by interaction with the controlling device acting upon an application creates new meanings. He breaks down the experience of narrative within an interactive environment into several

strands which include: the possible paths that can be taken, the sense of incompleteness or 'missingness' when engaging with an onscreen narrative – which can be interpreted as paths never ventured and experiences missed, multi-modality: combining more than one sensory experience, conditions of predictability and the ergodic: narrative brought into being by the 'non-trivial' actions of the reader. These strands create narratives and emotional responses beyond that programmed into the application, with new meanings added and emotions experienced by the user in terms of their response, experience and action.

Methods

This research project maps user-centred research onto craft thinking and methodologies, using the rigour of user-centred research and the insights of craft practice: making the implicit knowledge and assumptions of the craft-maker explicit through the methodologies of design. Embedding craft notions into all elements of programming and digital imaging provides a new focus for HCI user testing; one that uses the instrumentality, symbolism and aesthetics (Rafaeli and Vilnai-Yavetz 2003) of the jewellery object as an emotional stimulus that affects the user's sense making of the digital object. In effect, a new hybrid object, that is a synthesis of the physical and virtual, is perceived.

The application of user testing is standard within Design and many other disciplines. User testing responses were analysed using the POINT Framework (Bontoft 2006). The POINT Framework was developed by Martin Bontoft and colleagues in Human Factors at IDEO¹ to simplify and objectify the categorisation of research findings. It is used to identify:

Problems: *areas in which people currently experience difficulty*

Opportunities: *possibilities to use ideas that the designer has already formulated*

Insights: *divergence, unexpected/surprising results*

Needs: *user needs or perceived user needs*

Themes: *multiple convergent responses*

¹ IDEO is a design consultancy based in Palo Alto, CA, with other offices in San Francisco, Chicago, Boston, London, Munich and Shanghai. The Point Framework was developed to analyse the products of user-research at IDEO hosted co-design workshops.

The POINT framework of analysis is specific to IDEO. The researchers selected it as this type of analysis closely reflects the implicit analysis undertaken by visual artists and craftspeople within practice. The framework enabled existing knowledge and assumptions to be tested against user experience.

Approach

This paper discusses an initial evaluative user-testing study undertaken in 2006. Jewellery and multimedia content were created by the authors to gather data regarding participants' emotional responses to the experience of jewellery as a controlling device to an onscreen interaction. The user group comprised 4 participants.

Participants were observed and videoed and asked to complete a 'response sheet' (Figure 1) after experiencing each of the following four scenarios:

- Wearing a piece of their own jewellery, which they had been asked to bring to the session: described in analysis as 'own jewellery'.
- Wearing a simple steel and gold plate neckpiece with a bird/heart motif (depending on interpretation). Described in analysis as 'new jewellery'. This was intended to be aesthetically bland and neutral.
- Wearing the 'new jewellery' with a sensor. An interaction was simulated with an onscreen digital animation of birds emanating from a point on the screen and flying away. Each new bird generated triggered a musical note selected at random from a pre-recorded scale. A synthesized flute sound was chosen to represent birdsong. The number of birds appearing and the intensity of the music increased as the participant moved closer to the screen and diminished as they moved away.
- Wearing their own jewellery with a sensor simulating the same interaction as above.

1.2 Artefact1

Please put on the piece of jewellery in front of a mirror. Either sketch or describe what the jewellery looks like in the red box below. From the lists, please highlight any emotions evoked by the jewellery. You may write anywhere in the space below (and overleaf) to add any further comments.

Acceptance		Joy
Anger		Jealousy
Anticipation		Love
Boredom		Regret
Disgust		Remorse
Envy		Sadness
Fear		Shame
Guilt		Sorrow
Hate		Surprise
Hope		

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Figure 1 Response Sheet

The response sheet (Figure 1) listed a range of emotions: acceptance, anger, anticipation, boredom, disgust, envy, fear, guilt, hate, hope, joy, jealousy, love, regret, remorse, sadness, shame, sorrow, surprise. The sheet included large areas of white space. Participants were asked to draw or describe the jewellery object in the red box, then highlight any emotions that they experienced. They were asked to use the remainder of the page and overleaf to make any further comments they wished. This ‘freeform’ approach to a questionnaire allowed participants to adopt whatever approach they felt appropriate to their experience, from a minimal “No feelings towards this piece”, to detailed narratives explaining both how and why they felt particular emotions. (Figure 2)

1.2 Artefact1

Please put on the piece of jewellery in front of a mirror. Either sketch or describe what the jewellery looks like in the red box below. From the lists, please highlight any emotions evoked by the jewellery. You may write anywhere in the space below (and overleaf) to add any further comments.

I feel as if it would take time for me to accept the jewellery being in the environment in which I wear it.

I feel as if I am anticipating something from the jewellery.

I like the relationship between the shape in itself, looking in the kind of shape on the inside screen, but I feel that I might dislike or change the necklace because it feels quite delicate - or that I might change the shape on the screen. I'm curious about what to do...

exchange - as I wear it more I want to play with the necklace & find out almost change it to see what would happen.

I feel as if the shape attached to the head but I don't feel like a happy cat or head.

I'm not sure to the primary necklace.

Because I am not sure to the item I don't feel confident in it. I feel that the item gets lost on me.

The item doesn't really feel like me, it's lightweight - I feel quite clumsy in it.

I would be tremendously much the necklace as I see my own, to kind of build an association/consent to relationship with it. I feel the need to get use to it.

I would change the shape on the screen because it feel like not accurate in the shape's color.

Acceptance		Joy
Anger		Jealousy
Anticipation		Love
Boredom		Regret
Disgust		Remorse
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Figure 2 Completed Response Sheet

The initial test using the participants own jewellery was designed to allow the participants to familiarise themselves with three elements: the response sheet itself, how they understood the

emotions stated on the response sheet and how one might discuss a jewellery object in relation to emotion.

Analysis

The response sheets were analysed to discover the participants' reactions to using jewellery as a controlling device to interactivity using the POINT Framework:

Problems: areas in which people currently experience difficulty

Opportunities: possibilities to use ideas that the designer has already formulated

Insights: divergence, unexpected/surprising results

Needs: user needs or perceived user needs

Themes: multiple convergent responses

Problems:

- Jewellery cannot be 'neutral'
- Participants 'own' jewellery has emotional associations which cannot be 're-wired'
- People don't expect jewellery to be interactive

Opportunities:

- Wearers expect jewellery to have 'special powers'
- Using jewellery as a controlling device creates new and pleasurable experiences
- Interaction adds new emotional meaning to jewellery and to screen based content

Insights:

- Interactivity creates a sense of attachment to a previously unattractive object
- Interactivity enhances emotions already associated with jewellery
- Interactivity makes jewellery 'talk'

Needs:

- Wearers want jewellery to interact in a playful and fun way
- Jewellery must be comfortable and easy to wear
- Interaction should be specific to the wearer (see potential Princess below)

Themes:

- Wearers perceive interactivity as increasing the 'value' of jewellery
- Wearers have a deep emotional attachment to jewellery
- Wearers identify the interaction as an extension of their own existing emotional responses towards jewellery

Findings

Problems – things that need to be rectified:

For interaction between wearer and screen based content to be a positive and meaningful experience the interaction should be triggered by jewellery with which the wearer is comfortable and had a sense of familiarity. Jewellery cannot of course be neutral: the minimalist design of the 'new' jewellery (Figure 3) was unappealing and as such it evoked limited or negative emotional responses.

Figure 3, stainless steel, silver and goldplate necklace

It was perceived as too delicate and wearers feared that they might break it. It made some wearers feel clumsy and in some cases did not evoke any emotions at all. Although designed to be 'plain', inevitably it was 'read' by the wearer. Moingnard (2005) suggests, the wearer or viewer of jewellery will try and find significance beyond the object itself. This manifested itself as a reading as a broken heart, or disappointment by the wearer that it could not be easily 'read'. When the sensor was attached to one participants own jewellery, there was discordance: the interaction was seen as being related to the sensor rather than the jewellery.

The participant described the meaning embodied in their jewellery as fixed, and therefore they were unable to connect the new, unfamiliar interaction with their own familiar jewellery. An association was made between the shape the participants were asked to walk towards on the screen and the wire 'bird' on the necklace, this was intended, however the shape onscreen did not reflect the shape on the necklace closely enough and this was perceived as confusing. None of the participants described the motif on the neckpiece as a bird, most described it as a heart, and in some cases a broken heart.

Opportunities – things we expected

Peacock's 'Boundary of Translation' (Figure 4) was reached within seconds by three-quarters of the participants: the moment when they understood that the jewellery/sensor was a controlling device for the animation. This understanding was evident as the participant's faces 'lit up' as they realised the cause and effect of the jewellery acting upon the screen based animation. One participant did not recognise her involvement in the interaction until the sensor was combined with her own jewellery.

QuickTime™ and a
Noise Decompressor
are needed to see this picture.

Figure 4, Boundary of Translation (after Peacock, 2004)

Jewellery was identified as being worn on particular occasions: for occasions when the wearer expected to have fun and be entertained. Wearing jewellery makes the wearer feel confident, and full of anticipation, expecting that good things will happen to them, and that they will attract welcome attention. Some considered their jewellery to be a kind of 'amulet', which

made them more powerful and could be played with to calm nerves. It was also described as symbolising love and joy, related to the circumstances in which it was received as a gift.

Insights - things we didn't expect

When the new jewellery was 'enabled' and the wearer triggered the interactive animation, one participant felt a sense of 'ownership' – that they now 'wanted' the piece of jewellery.

Another participant described feeling ownership of the digital media. A direct connection was made between notions of ownership relating to traditional jewellery objects and the multimedia content. Participants described building a relationship with the new jewellery object through the interaction and being able to make the jewellery 'speak'. Even when no emotions at all had been experienced in wearing the new jewellery alone, when it was enabled the same participant described experiencing anticipation, hope and joy.

The interaction could enhance emotions and make explicit emotions already implicit within a jewellery object. When the sensor was worn with one participant's own jewellery, which had evoked negative emotions of sadness and regret, connecting the sensor and triggering the interaction was an upsetting experience: the participant described a sense of releasing some of the emotions that the jewellery represented. Participants described feelings of confidence and fun when their own jewellery triggered the interaction and even a strong feeling that their own jewellery was now 'talking' to them, relaying the narrative associated with receiving the jewellery: this feeling prompted them to move close to the screen to increase the intensity of the interaction. The meaning and emotional significance of the digital object was altered by the wearers' attachment to the jewellery.

Needs – what people want or think they want

People feel they would engage with interactive jewellery that is physically similar to that which they already own. It did appear that participants would emotionally engage with a piece of jewellery that created an interaction, and that the interaction could enhance emotions and make explicit emotions already implicit within a jewellery object. One participant suggested enabling the jewellery to create a projection when entering a social gathering describing the enabled jewellery as: "great for potential princesses".

One participant expressed disappointment that she could not control the shape of the birds' flight paths. (Figure 5) Another said she would have liked to change the shape of the virtual bird by manipulating the jewellery object.

Figure 5, Bird Animation

Themes – common threads

All the participants had emotional responses to wearing their own jewellery, but were in some cases surprised that they had not recognised or articulated this implicit quality in their jewellery before taking part in the testing. Participants were surprised by the interaction and their perceived ability to control the interaction. It was described as ‘very human, not technical’. Once participants understood the interaction they wanted to explore how their movements might create different sequences or sounds in the projected image. When the new jewellery object was understood to have an interactive quality, participants became accepting and described this as a ‘value’.

Conclusions

The research results suggest that a new synthesis can be made between the jeweller’s craft and multimedia design, both in practice methodology and shared concept. This relationship is likely to develop new hybrid craft practices and new aesthetics that enhance emotional response in the field of tangible computing. Analysis of user testing utilising the POINT Framework proved to be a viable research method. The structure and categorization used, provided valuable information in this context. The researchers intend to direct further research responding directly to issues highlighted in test results. Past research work (White and Steel 2005) has focused on utilizing the physical structure of the jewellery object as a control mechanism for multimedia content (Figure 6).

Figure 6, Link Controlled Multimedia

User testing, as outlined, has suggested that this approach, combined with a jewellery specific narrative, may extend emotional response to the jewellery/multimedia synthesis. Further experimentation with and testing of the relationship between the physical form of the jewellery and the visual design of multimedia content will be the basis of future research.

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